

Ethnomedicinal plants used to treat gastro-intestinal disorders & related ailments by the tribals of Mount Parasnath, District Giridih, (Jharkhand), India

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Abstract

An ethnobotanical study of Mount Parasnath in district Giridih, Jharkhand have been carried out by the tribal, who live in dense forest for away from the hospitals. The local inhabitants have developed and preserved a very old & strong tradition for folk medicine. This presentment brings out 30 medicinal plant species belonging to 24 families used specially for the treatment of “gastro-intestinal disorders and related ailments”.

Key words : Mount Parasnath, Tribals, Ethno-medicine, Gastro-intestinal disorders.

Mount Parasnath lies in the mid-eastern part of Chotanagpur highland which located between 86°03' E to 86°14' E longitudes and 23°55' N to 24°01' N latitudes, it form the southern parts of Giridih district.

Literature relating to Indian medicinal plants has considerably studied^{1-6,10}. Present work gives a comprehensive account on the therapeutic efficiency of several plants curing ‘Gastro-intestinal disorders’. It is a common disease in summer season due to contaminated water drinking, open stool discharges, wrong feeding habits, etc.

Ethnomedicobotanical survey were conducted in more then 15 remote villages in Parasnath hill and adjoining areas from January

2003 to January 2005. Interviews were conducted, information were collected, personal contact were made with the herbal practitioners. Plant and plant products used in the remedies of diseases, mode of preparation of the drugs, method of administration and doses were noted. Herbarium, standard books and literatures were consulted for identification and nomenclature of species.

Total 30 medicinal plants were collected for the treatment of ‘Gastro-intestinal disorders’ and arranged alphabetically. Botanical name, Family, Local name and Traditional uses are given below-

Acacia catechu Willd. (Mimosaceae, Khair or Katha) RVY 13013
Bark astringent given internally thrice a day

for few days to cure acidity of the stomach.

Bauhinia malabarica Roxb. (Caesalpinaceae, Karmai or Amla or Imli) RVY 13030

Young flowers chewed orally twice a day for three days to cure dysentery.

Berberis asiatica Roxb. (Berberidaceae, Rasaut) RVY 13047

Dried root bark powder 2-4 gm given twice a day for one week to control diarrhoea and jaundice.

Bombax ceiba L. (Bombacaceae, Semul or Simal) RVY 13092

Gum is taken in warm water twice a day to cure diarrhoea and dysentery.

Butea monosperma (Lamk.) Taub. (Papilionaceae, Palas or Dhak) RVY 13010

Gum is taken in warm water thrice a day to cure diarrhoea.

Capparis zeylanica L. (Capparidaceae, Ardanda) RVY 13059

Bark paste (2-4 gm) is used with water twice a day for one week to cure stomach ache & cholera.

Centratherum anthelminticum (L.) Kuntze (Asteraceae, Somraj) RVY 13032

Dried powder of whole plant (5-10 gm) with warm water is given orally twice a day for one week to remove hookworm and thread worms from stomach. Roasted seeds eaten to cure stomachache.

Croton roxburghii Balak. (Euphorbiaceae, Chucka) RVY 13066

A bark paste (5 gm) is given with water thrice a day for 3-4 days to treat liver diseases.

Curculigo orchidoides Gaertn. (Amaryllidaceae, Kalimusli) RVY 13177

Rhizome paste is given in warm water orally

thrice a day for a month to cure piles, jaundice and diarrhoea.

Dalbergia latifolia Roxb. (Papilionaceae, Lalshisham) RVY 13128

Dried whole plant powder (2-3 gm) with plain water is given orally in one dose for a day in 4-5 days to cure stomachache diarrhoea & dysentery.

Desmodium oojeinensis (Roxb.) Ohashi (Papilionaceae, Sandan) RVY 13048

Bark gum given twice a day with warm milk to cure diarrhoea.

Desmodium pulchellum Benth. (Papilionaceae, Lodrom) RVY 13003

Bark extract (2-3 teaspoons) is given orally thrice a day for one week to control diarrhoea.

Elephantopus scaber L. (Asteraceae, Karipadam) RVY 13143

Root extract (2-4 gm) given twice a day with warm water for a week to control diarrhoea, stomachache & dysentery.

Flacourtia romantchi L. Herit. (Flacourtiaceae, Bilangra) RVY 13132

Fruits are given in enlargement of spleen and liver, useful in curing jaundice.

Fragaria vesca L. (Rosaceae, Pahari rasbhari) RVY 13037

Leaves infusion taken 2 times a day for one week, controls diarrhoea.

Ficus bengalensis L. (Moraceae, Bar or Bargat) RVY 13056

Bark powder (5-6 gm) given orally twice a day for one month cures dysentery; fruits infusion (2-4 gm) given orally thrice a day for one week to control diarrhoea.

Geranium ocellatum Camb. (Geraniaceae)

RVY 13004

Dried whole plant powder (5-6 gm) is given with water twice a day for a week to control diarrhoea & intestine ulcers.

Helicteres isora L. (Sterculiaceae, Kapasi) RVY 13077

Dried fruits powder (5-6 gm) given orally twice a day for a month to cure intestinal disorders, colic pains & diarrhoea. Root extract (4-5 teaspoons) given orally twice a day for one week to control amoebic dysentery.

Holarrhena antidysentrica Wall. (Apocynaceae, Kurchi or Kewar) RVY 13018
Dried stem bark powder (4-5 gm) given twice a day to control dysentery, stomach pain, amoebic dysentery, colic pain, piles & spleen complaints.

Lagerstroemia reginae Roxb. (Lythraceae, Jarul) RVY 13063

Dried bark powder is stimulant & 2-3 gm given once a day for one week to control stomach pain & diarrhoea.

Micromeria capitellata Benth. (Lamiaceae, Lajauni) RVY 13103

Herb is source of peppermint given orally to improve digestion, hot infusion in stomachache.

Murraya paniculata (L.) Jack (Rutaceae, Kamini) RVY 13084

Leaves are stimulant & paste is given (2-3 tea spoons) orally for one week to cure diarrhoea.

Osbeckia stellata Ker. – Gawl. (Melastomaceae, Tsulesi) RVY 13137

Root extract (4-6 gm) given thrice a day for one month to improve digestion.

Shorea robusta Gaertn. f. (Dipterocarpaceae, Sal or Sakhu) RVY 13054

Resin (2-3 teaspoons) with water per day for one week to improve digestion & cure dysentery.

Smilax ovalifolia Roxb. (Liliaceae, Ramdatun) RVY 13167

Root paste (2-4 gm) given twice a day for one week to control dysentery.

Sonchus oleraceus L. (Asteraceae, Dudhi) RVY 13019

Dried powder of whole plant (5-10 gm) given twice a day for one week to control liver diseases, leaves and roots are used in indigestion.

Spermadictyon suaveolens Roxb. (Rubiaceae, Budolhighasi) RVY 13061

Root powder (2-4 gm) given thrice a day for one week to cure diarrhoea.

Terminalia bellirica (Gaertn.) Roxb. (Combretaceae, Bahera) RVY 13017

Fruits powder (2-3 teaspoons) twice a day for one month to cure piles & diarrhoea.

Terminalia chebula Retz obs. (Combretaceae, Harra) RVY 13029

Dried fruits powder (2-3 teaspoons) given twice a day for one month to cure chronic ulcer and stomachache.

Toona ciliata R. (Meliaceae, Tun or Red cedar) RVY 13101

Bark powder (4-6 gm) given thrice a day for one week to cure chronic infantile dysentery.

The study reveals that the tribal people living in remote area of Mount Parasnath (Giridih), Jharkhand utilize above listed medicinal plants for curing 'Gastro-intestinal disorders'.

These herbal therapies are very effective and give much relief. These plants do not have any side effect or reaction.

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